

SIMPLE VIEWS ABOUT ORAL AND WRITTEN TRANSLATION

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Annotation. This article is devoted to difference between oral written translation. Oral simultaneous translation is more complex. This is an interpretation of what is heard in real time. The difficulty of a simultaneous interpreter's work is that he has to instantly realize what the speaker is saying and immediately translate his speech to all listeners.

Key words: oral translation, written translation, word, phrases

Many people believe that translation activities are the same in all areas. Most people have little understanding of the difference between the work of a written and oral specialist. Considering that language knowledge will be enough, and whether spoken speech or text on paper is not so important.

In fact, oral and written translation have enormous differences. These are two directions independent of each other. Each of them requires its own knowledge and skills.

Below we will talk in more detail about each type of translation activity. And you will be able to understand the difference in them.

This knowledge will be useful to you if the need for interpretation or translation services arises. Understanding the intricacies of the process, you can easily select the specialist you need.

The difference between these areas of translation activity is huge. Basically, it lies in the skills required for use on the part of the translator, as well as the difficulties that the specialist encounters during his work.

In some languages, such as English, interpreters and translators are even called differently. Let's take a closer look at each of them below.

A specialist in this area must have a high level of knowledge of the grammar and punctuation of the two languages with which he works. In addition, it is important to have good writing style. It is necessary that the translator can not only correctly interpret words and phrases in the desired language, but also find analogues that are missing in it.

You must be able to correctly translate abbreviations, abbreviations, as well as hints and omissions. Each language has its own. In addition, it is necessary to perfectly understand the style of the text being presented.

The specialist must have a good command of the languages with which he works. He must be able to accurately capture and convey the linguistic and semantic nuances of the translated material. Its task is not always to convey text word for word. He must interpret the material to convey the meaning as accurately as possible. Even small inaccuracies in the presentation are allowed.

It can be said that a translator works in a "one-dimensional" aspect. The source of his activity is words written on paper. The result is similar words, also written on paper.

What simplifies the work of a translator is that he has enough time to search and select words, think about and check his work. In addition, he has the opportunity to use various auxiliary materials (dictionaries, glossaries and other sources on the topic).

The translator is free to manage his own work schedule. He can take a break at a time convenient for himself. We can say that this specialist works in a psychologically comfortable environment.

Interpretation and work of a specialist in this profile

As for this area of translation activity, completely different skills and abilities are required. The interpreter must be as collected and prepared as possible.

An interpreter must:

- have the deepest spoken knowledge of two languages at once,
- be able to translate, both in one and in another direction,
- understand spoken language,
- be able not to get confused when the speaker speaks at a fast pace, has an accent or has speech impediments,
- have excellent memory and other skills.

His work is complicated by a rather tense psychological environment, activity schedule, as well as the lack of auxiliary materials at hand. Unlike a translator, he cannot find a word unknown to him, see if he interpreted a particular term correctly, or double-check himself several times.

There are enough difficulties in the work of a specialist in this profile. The psychological pressure is many times higher. He has to find a solution to a particular linguistic problem almost instantly. Only your own knowledge remains to help.

In addition to the task of translation, this specialist is entrusted with the function of a kind of bridge between two parties who do not understand each other. At the same time, those who want to come to a common solution to their problems.

Here it is important to be to some extent a psychologist, and to some extent a diplomat. We must remain calm and neutral in any situation. It is necessary to be able to negotiate even in a tense situation. The ability to smooth out conflict situations is also welcome.

The appearance of the interpreter must necessarily correspond to the event being held. It is better to clarify in advance where and how it will take place, and dress accordingly.

As you understand, the role of an interpreter is deeper and more complex than that of a translator. In such work, it is important not just to know languages, it is necessary to understand people and be able to find contact with them.

In addition to everything, it should be noted that interpretation is divided into two types: simultaneous and consecutive. Each of them is also unique in its own way.

Consecutive interpreting is usually typical for business meetings and negotiations. The speaker usually pauses briefly and gives the interpreter time to convey his thoughts to those around him. Consequently, the linguist has a short period of time to understand and interpret the speaker's speech for himself. As the conclusion we can say that These are the main differences between these areas of translation activity. If you are a translation customer, we hope our material helped you understand the features of each direction and understand how to select a specialist.

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